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Review

TOXICOLOGICAL HAIR ANALYSIS USING DIFFERENT TECHNIQUES: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Hair drug analysis is known to be an advanced toxicological method, used for retrospective examination of substance use over extended periods. This study aims to discuss the drug incorporation mechanisms and impact of pre-analytical processes such as segmentation, decontamination, and extraction. Additionally, this study has evaluated important analytical techniques like GC-MS and LC-MS- highlighting superiority of LC-MS for low-dose and thermolabile compounds. The result of the study has emphasized the importance of proper methodology and interpretation expertise in differentiating active use from passive exposure. With the non-invasive nature and broad detection window, hair analysis holds significant clinical and forensic value. Future directions include the formulation and implementation of standardization protocols, utilization of high-resolution mass spectrometry, and integration of data-driven models for the improvement in accuracy and legal defensibility.

Key words: Hair drug analysis, drug incorporation mechanism, analytical techniques, accuracy, legal

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1. INTRODUCTION

Hair drug testing represents an emerging technological advancement capable of identifying drug use over more extended periods compared to urine or blood analysis. However, there are still questions about how medications enter the hair and what factors affect their presence and retention (*Matey et al., 2021; Palamar & Salomone, 2023; Spiehler, 2000*). Diffusion from blood, perspiration, sebum, and skin, as well as exposure to the environment, are examples of possible drug entry routes (*"Drug Delivery Systems," 2015; Yu et al., 2021*). Drug binding to locations in the hair, such as melanin and protein elements, may be influenced by forces like electrostatic and van der Waals forces (*Cone, 1996; Larsson & Tjälve, 1979*). Studies have shown that, melanin concentration and hair colour may influence the mechanism of cocaine binding, which could lead to biases in hair testing based on ethnicity or hair colour (*Joseph et al., 1996; Mieczkowski & Kruger, 2007*). Given the limits of self-reports of drug use, drug testing is essential in clinical and forensic toxicology contexts to verify intoxication and assess the degree of drug-related impairment. The most objective way to diagnose drug usage is widely accepted to be chemical testing of bodily fluids, which uses the presence of drug metabolites as proof of exposure. Improvements in analytical methodology now allow the drug identification from unusual samples such as hair, even though the current standard for urine analysis involves initial immunoassay screening followed by confirmation using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (*Kintz, 2003; Wissenbach & Steuer, 2023*). Hair testing offers countless advantages over traditional methods such as urine and blood analysis. Hair stands out as a non-invasive, easily collectible medium that can be closely observed to minimize the risk of tampering in forensic scenarios (*Barroso & Gallardo, 2014; Jonathan Palmer, 2023*). Moreover, testing of hair provides an extended window of drug detection, spanning weeks to months, and in some cases even years (*Kintz, 2003; Kintz et al., 2006; Usman et al., 2019*). In due course, it has become increasingly recognized in diverse fields such as doping control, therapeutic applications, forensic sciences, and pre-employment screening. Notably, since attempts to avoid urinalysis do not influence the results of hair analysis, hair testing can be effectively used in conjunction with urine-based drug testing methods (*DuPont & Baumgartner, 1995; Hung et al., 2024*).

THE OBJECTIVE OF THIS STUDY

Is to highlight the importance of hair morphology in determining drug using history, the timeframe of exposure and potential environmental contact.

This study will also emphasize on drug classification, potential risks associated with addiction, legal frameworks and routes of drug administration that affect detection. Analytical tools such as GC-MS and LC-MS will be evaluated for their accuracy in drug detection, particularly in distinguishing actual drug use from contamination.

2. HAIR MORPHOLOGY AND DRUG ANALYSIS

It is important to emphasize that identifying drugs in a person's system based solely on hair morphology is insufficient. However, hair morphology can provide valuable information about the characteristics and growth patterns of hair, which is helpful for analysing drug test results from hair samples.

Hair morphology can provide relevant information in the following areas:

2.1. Timeframe of drug use:

Since hair grows at an average rate of approximately 1 cm per month, the length of hair sample can serve as an indicator of the time frame during which uses of drugs may have occurred. For example, a 5-centimeter hair sample could suggest drug use within the past 5 months (*Rotolo et al., 2021*).

2.2. History of drug use:

The distribution of drugs along the hair shaft can provide valuable insights into an individual's drug use history (*del Ramirez Fernández et al., 2025*). For example, a higher concentration of drugs near the hair root might indicate recent drug use (*Usman et al., 2019; Yan et al., 2021*).

2.3. Environmental exposure:

Hair morphology can also provide insights into environmental drug exposure, including scenarios such as second-hand smoke. In cases where drugs are detected in hair despite the individual's denial of personal use, it is possible that the substances were absorbed from the

surrounding environment (Papaseit et al.,2011; Wang & Cone,1995).

3. CLASSIFICATION OF DRUGS

Drugs are categorized according to their effects and uses. They are-

3.1. Medical Drugs:

Medical drugs are used to cure the diseases and medical condition. They are prescribed by healthcare professionals and can be purchased at pharmacies with a prescription. To guarantee safety and effectiveness, medications go through stringent testing and approval procedures (Asif Khan, 2023).

3.2. Recreational Drugs:

Recreational drugs are substances used for their psychoactive effects, altering a person's mood, perception, and behavior. Examples include alcohol, hallucinogens, cannabis, opioids, sedatives, and stimulants. These drugs are commonly used for pleasure or to enhance social experiences but can also carry risks including the potential for dependence and addiction (Begun & Murray,2020).

3.3. Illicit Drugs:

Substances that are prohibited by law from being produced, possessed, or distributed are known as illicit drugs. Few examples include Cocaine, heroin, methamphetamine, LSD, and ecstasy. The use of illegal drugs can lead to serious health complications and is often associated with criminal activity (Aanstoos,2024).

4. RISKS AND SIDE EFFECTS:

All drugs, whether over-the-counter or prescribed, bear certain risks and potential side effects. These effects can range from mild and temporary symptoms to severe reactions or long-term health issues. It is important to follow prescribed dosages, consult healthcare professionals and be aware of potential interactions with other substances (Preuss et al.,2019). Drug abuse refers to the non-medical, intentional, and excessive use of drugs, often resulting in adverse consequences on an individual's physical and mental health (Harkey,1993). Examples of drug misuse include using someone else's prescription, taking larger doses than advised, using medicines in ways not recommended by doc-

tor. Harm reduction strategies are designed to alleviate the adverse consequences associated with drug use. These approaches encompass initiatives such as needle exchange programs, safe consumption sites, and educational campaigns that promote responsible drug use and aim to reduce associated risks.

5. LEGAL AND REGULATORY FRAMEWORK

The legality of drugs significantly varies across different countries and jurisdictions. Some substances are tightly regulated and only available with a prescription, while others are strictly prohibited (Benjamin & Chidi, 2014; Oluwole et al., 2024). Laws and regulations regarding drug control are designed to balance public health concerns, societal values, and individual rights (Burke-Shyne et al., 2017; Seear, 2024). It is essential to emphasize that although it is endeavored to furnish accurate and current information, it is always advisable to seek guidance from healthcare professionals, reputable sources, and local regulations for precise and up-to-date details on drugs.

6. DRUG ADMINISTRATION ROUTES:

When a drug is administered, it can enter the body through various methods, and its absorption and distribution depend on the route of administration (Benet, 1978; "General Considerations," 2015; Hedaya, 2024). Here are some common routes of drug administration and how drugs are infused into the body:

6.1. Oral Administration:

Medications can be given orally as liquids, powders, tablets, or capsules. The medication enters the body through the digestive tract, where it is broken down and absorbed into the bloodstream via the intestines or stomach walls (Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Health Care (IQWiG), 2006).

6.2. Injection:

Injections can be used to deliver medications to different parts of the body. Subcutaneous (SC), intramuscular (IM), and intravenous (IV) injections are common injection routes. By injecting the medication straight into a vein, intravenous injections enable quick and thorough bloodstream absorption (Röhrich & Kauert, 1997). The medicine is injected into muscle tissue or

beneath the skin for SC and IM injections, respectively, and then progressively reaches the bloodstream. Inhalation: Certain medications can be breathed into the lungs, where the lung tissues absorb them and release them into the bloodstream (*Nt Contributor, 2003*).

6.3. Direct Inhalation:

Inhalation can occur through methods such as smoking, vaporizing, or using inhalers. Because of the huge surface area of lungs and fast blood flow, this route enables quick absorption (*Patton & Byron, 2007*).

6.4. Topical Application:

Drugs can be applied topically as gels, patches, ointments, or creams. They enter the bloodstream after being absorbed through the skin. This method is frequently used to treat skin diseases or provide local effects like pain alleviation (*Bani & Bhardwaj, 2021; Bhowmik, 2012; Flynn, 1996*).

6.5. Transdermal Patch:

Transdermal patches are specifically designed to slowly release drugs through the skin over an extended period. The drug is infused into the patch, which adheres to the skin, allowing for continuous absorption into the bloodstream (*Bird & Ravindra, 2020; Jasti et al., 2021; Tiwari et al., 2022*).

Figure 1: Drug Transportation in Hair (Source: Srogi, 2006)

6.6. Sublingual and Buccal Administration:

Certain drugs, such as some kinds of pills or sprays, can be applied to the cheek (buccal) or under the tongue (sublingual). Bypassing the digestive system, the medication reaches the bloodstream straight after being absorbed through the mucosal membranes in these regions (*Tricia Kinman, 2017*).

7. DRUG ABSORPTION INTO HAIR:

Drug absorption into hair, also known as drug incorporation or drug deposition in hair, is a process by which drugs and their metabolites from the bloodstream become incorporated into the hair strands (**Shown in figure 1**). Hair can act as a useful biomarker for detecting drug use and exposure over an extended period compared to other biological samples like urine or blood. The reason behind this is that medications and their byproducts can linger in hair for weeks or months after being consumed (*Klein et al., 2000; Pragst & Balikova, 2006; Srogi, 2006*).

The process of drug incorporation into hair occurs through the following steps:

7.1. Drug Circulation in Bloodstream:

After consumption, drugs are absorbed into the bloodstream. The drug molecules and their metabolites then circulate throughout the body, including the hair follicles (*Bertol & Favretto, 2022*).

7.2. Passive Diffusion into Hair:

The bloodstream passively diffuses drugs and their metabolites into the growing hair shafts inside the hair follicles. The anagen (growing) phase of the hair, which lasts for several months, is when this integration mostly occurs (*Chourasia & Jain, 2009; Farah, 2020; Patzelt & Lademann, 2013*).

7.3. Binding to Melanin:

Most drugs are believed to be incorporated into hair by binding to melanin, the pigment responsible for hair color. Melanin is present in varying concentrations in different hair types and colors, and drugs tend to bind more effectively to darker, melanin rich hair (*Aubry, 2002; Cone, 1996; Fernández et al., 2020*).

7.4. Gradual Accumulation:

As the hair grows, the drug molecules become embedded in the hair shaft, resulting in a timeline of drug use or exposure (*Boumba et al., 2006*).

8. DRUG ABSORPTION INTO HAIR ACCORDING TO ACIDIC AND BASIC NATURE OF DRUG:

Chemical characteristics of drugs, such as their acidity

or basicity, affect how well they are absorbed into hair. Like the way drugs are absorbed in the body, the ionization state of the drug in the bloodstream can affect its incorporation into hair. But it is crucial to remember that drug integration into hair is a complicated process, and variables other than the drug's basicity or acidity might also be quite essential (Welch et al., 1993).

8.1. Acidic Drugs in Hair Incorporation:

Acidic drugs, which tend to be ionized in basic environments (higher pH), are less likely to incorporate into hair effectively because hair is predominantly composed of keratin, a protein-based structure with a slightly acidic pH (around 4.5 to 5.5). In the bloodstream, where the pH is close to neutral (around 7.4), acidic drugs may exist predominantly in their ionized form, making it difficult for them to bind to hair effectively (Röhrich & Kauert, 1997). As a result, acidic drugs might have lower levels of incorporation into hair, and their detection in hair samples could be limited.

8.2. Basic Drugs in Hair Incorporation:

Basic drugs, which tend to be ionized in acidic environments (lower pH), may have a higher affinity for hair incorporation compared to acidic drugs. In the bloodstream, where the pH is around 7.4, basic drugs may exist predominantly in their non-ionized, lipophilic form, which could facilitate their binding to hair effectively. The basic nature of certain drugs may enhance their incorporation into hair, allowing for more extended detection windows in hair samples compared to other drugs (Cirimele et al., 1997).

9. FACTORS AFFECTING DRUG INCORPORATION INTO HAIR

Apart from the acidic or basic nature of drugs, several other factors can affect drug incorporation into hair:

9.1. Lipid Solubility:

The lipophilicity of a drug (its ability to dissolve in fats) can influence its incorporation into hair. More lipophilic drugs have greater tendency to bind to the hair structure.

9.2. Melanin Content:

Hair contains melanin, and many drugs exhibit higher binding affinity to melanin-rich hair, particularly in individuals with darker hair colors.

9.3. Drug Dose and Frequency of Use:

Higher drug doses and more frequent use of drugs can lead to increased drug levels in hair samples.

9.4. Hair Characteristics:

Characteristics of hair such as color, porosity and thickness can also influence drug bonding. Darker and thicker hair tends to exhibit higher levels of drug incorporation (Kintz et al., 2004).

9.5. External Contamination:

External exposure to drugs—such as from environmental contamination or drug smoke, can also lead to the presence of drug residues on the hair surface. However, these external contaminants are typically distinguishable from drugs that are internal incorporated.

It is important to emphasize that hair drug testing is a complex process, and the interpretation of results must be approached with caution, considering all the factors that can influence drug incorporation into hair.

10. HAIR DRUG TESTING

10.1. Documentation and steps involved in Hair drug analysis:

The significance of pre-scientific strides in hair examination is frequently misjudged. In view of the idea of testing, the hair test ought to be gathered by research center staff. If this is not conceivable, a plainly composed assortment convention ought to be given (Pichini et al., 2004). Since the choice of hair fragment lengths and ensuing scientific techniques rely upon case history and hair test attributes, all significant data ought to be gotten and irrefutable. Different measures (shown in figure 2) should be taken to guarantee that there is no tainting in hair tests (Mizuno et al., 1994).

10.2. Hair Analysis Steps Segmentation:

Segmentation of hair is most important factor in analysing the drug present in the hair as these segments of hair can disclose the huge identification factors. The process of hair segmentation during hair drug analysis involves dividing the hair sample into discrete segments to analyze different time periods of drug exposure because drugs and their metabolites can be integrated into hair as it grows, this enables researchers or forensic analysts to identify patterns of drug usage

over time (Cone et al., 1991). By segmenting the hair, they can pinpoint when specific drug usage occurred and gain insights into a person's drug history. The segmentation of hairs can be done in progressive length manner so, as to occupy the drug amount as much as possible. Various conventional methods are being utilized to divide the hairs into segments one of the methods is to place the hair on the folded graph paper (Goullé et al., 2003). The gradations of the graph paper are used to align the hairs and cut them into segments in a methodical manner.

10.3. Decontamination:

Decontamination is the crucial and important step in removing the contaminants and other hindering particles from the hair. Usually, decontamination is processed because of two reasons first is to remove wax, shampoo e.tc. Secondly, decontamination is utilized to remove the drugs adhered to the hair from the environment which can be the reason of false results. So, to preserve these results the first wash of hair segments must be stored in the proper containers for tests that can be utilized in subsequent analysis (Thorspecken et al., 2004). The aim of sterilization is to remove impurities completely without harming the medication within the hair structure. Two types of solvents are commonly used for this purpose: protic and non-protic solvents. Protic solvents, like phosphate buffer or methanol, cause the hair to swell, leading to the release of the drug contained within it. On the contrary, aprotic solvents such as acetone or dichloromethane do not cause hair swelling, hence preserving the standard of the materials present in the hair structure (Welch et al., 1993).

The condition of hair strands mostly depends on the methods used to wash or decontaminate them. Various Procedures can be used for cleaning hair, such as using ethanol for some strands or for more intensive washing for others using methanol or acetone (Cirimele et al., 1997).

10.4. Extraction of Drugs from hair matrix:

There are no standardized strategies to remove medications from the hair matrix. The only effective way to extract the organic drugs from hair matrix requires either chemical digestion or solubilisation. Grinding the hair segments is another possible method but it may lead to the loss of drugs, already present in the matrix (Röhrich & Kauert, 1997).

Figure 2. Hair Drug Testing Process (Mizuno et al., 1994)

10.5. Methanol-assisted extraction:

A widely applicable method for the extraction of various drug compounds involves the use of methanol in an ultrasonic bath over a period of 5-18 hours. Due to the hydrophilic properties of methanol allow it to penetrate the hair matrix, causing swelling and facilitate the diffusion of drugs present. As an organic solvent, methanol effectively dissolves both lipophilic and neutral substances (Welch et al., 1993).

The ultrasonic treatment significantly degrades

the hair structure, enhancing drug release. This method allows the identification of sensitive drugs like heroin and lipophilic drugs like THC from the same extract. In certain cases, especially when medicines are present in high concentrations, the methanol extract can be immediately injected for GC-MS analysis (Cairns *et al.*, 2004). The possibility of a comparatively high degree of impurities in the extract is a disadvantage, though. Consequently, it is usually advised to perform a secondary cleanup process that involves either liquid/liquid extraction or solid-phase extraction. Even though using an ultrasonic bath to extract methanol takes a lengthy time, drug recovery is frequently insufficient and lower than with other extraction methods. When identifying fatty acid ethyl esters, which are alcohol indicators, researchers have seen the production of methyl esters throughout this process. Since this re-esterification process is significantly less common without ultrasonic treatment, it is thought to be influenced by the high local cavitation energy created during ultrasonication within the hair matrix (Kintz *et al.*, 2004; Kintz & Cirimele, 1997; Mizuno *et al.*, 1994; Welch *et al.*, 1993).

10.6. Aqueous acid or buffer solution assisted extraction:

The use of aqueous acidic solutions, usually in the range of 0.01 to 0.5 M HCl or phosphate buffer at pH 6.4 or 7.6, can effectively extract basic substances such as opiates, cocaine and its metabolites, amphetamines, and methadone. Protonation is a step in this extraction process that increases extraction efficiency (Kintz *et al.*, 2004; Kintz & Cirimele, 1997). Sometimes an enzymatic mixture of glucuronidase/arylsulfatase is used to detect any deposited metabolites. These aqueous extracts yield far cleaner results than methanol extracts. It is important to recognize, nevertheless, that some hydrolysis may take place during the extraction process, converting 6-monoacetylmorphine to morphine and cocaine to benzoylecgonine. These changes must therefore be considered. For example, despite being well deposited, heroin diacetylmorphine is usually not found in aqueous hair extracts (Thorspecken *et al.*, 2004).

10.7. Breaking down the hair matrix using enzymatic digestion:

Pronase and Proteinase K enzymes are proficient in breaking down hair proteins through the process of

hydrolysis. The presence of dithiothreitol can significantly enhance enzymatic digestion by reducing disulfide bonds, either during or prior to enzyme treatment. For example, 100 mg of Proteinase K and 200 mg of dithiothreitol in 60 mL of Tris buffer at pH 8.0 were used to thoroughly digest 10–30 mg of hair, which was then incubated for 4–6 hours at 37 °C. It is important to remember that there are other additional enzymatic techniques accessible (Annamalai *et al.*, 2023; Cairns *et al.*, 2004).

10.8. The treatment of hair using a water-based solution of NaOH for breakdown:

To extract drugs that demonstrate stability when subjected to alkaline conditions from hair, a convenient method involves utilizing an aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide (1 mol/L) at 80 °C for one hour. Numerous chemicals, such as nicotine, amphetamines, THC, antidepressants, neuroleptics, and other medications, benefit greatly from this alkaline extraction method. When combined with headspace solid phase microextraction (HS-SPME) for semi-volatile compounds, it usually allows for the quantitative recovery of these medications from the hair matrix and can be automated (Skopp *et al.*, 1997).

10.9. METHODS FOR ANALYSING DRUGS IN HAIR USING VARIOUS ANALYTICAL

10.9.1 Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry:

Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry combines the advantages of mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and gas chromatographic mechanism (shown in figure 3) to separate and identify chemicals in complex mixtures (Tagliaro *et al.*, 2000). This technique has a wide range of application including drug detection, fire investigation, explosive investigation, environmental analysis, and sample identification. Like liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS), GC-MS allows the detection and analysis of trace amounts of chemicals (Thiblin *et al.*, 2000).

Analysing drugs in hair heavily depends on gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), which is a potent analytical method for finding and classifying medications and their metabolites in hair samples. The following are GC-MS's primary functions in drug hair analysis:

Figure 3 GC MS credits <https://www.tech>

a) Sensitivity and Selectivity:

Because of its excellent sensitivity, GC-MS can identify medications and their metabolites in hair samples at extremely low concentrations. Moreover, it provides enhanced selectivity, allowing for the accurate identification of various chemical components within the sample (Mizuno et al.,1994; Skopp et al.,1997).

b) Identification of Various Drugs:

GC-MS hair analysis allows simultaneous detection of various drugs and their metabolites in single sample. This feature is particularly helpful when comprehensive assessment of an individual's drug use history is needed.

c) Long Detection Window:

GC-MS-based hair analysis is useful for retrospective drug use investigations due to the long detection window of drugs and their metabolites in hair, which can span from months to years depending on the length of the hair strand (Pichini et al.,2004).

d) Non-Invasive Sampling:

Compared to other biological matrices such as blood or urine; hair sample collection is non-invasive and relatively simple. This benefits both the subject and the analyst.

e) Difference between External Contamination and Ingested Drugs:

GC-MS analysis aids in differentiating between drugs that are externally deposited on the hair (e.g., through environmental exposure) and those that were ingested and subsequently incorporated into the hair shaft (Pichini et al.,2004).

f) Forensic and Clinical Applications:

GC-MS based drug in hair analysis is widely implemented in forensic investigation, work place drug testing and in monitoring drug compliance within substance abuse treatment programs.

g) Harmonious to Other Analytical Techniques:

The breadth and accuracy of drug detection in hair samples can be enhanced by combining GC-MS with other analytical techniques like liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS).

All things considered, GC-MS is the most convenient method for drug hair analysis, providing accurate and consistent results when evaluating a long-term drug exposure history. As such, it is a crucial technique in various fields, including clinical toxicology and forensic research.

Table I: Analytical detection of different drugs through GC-MS and LC-MS

Drug or metabolite	Technique used		
	GC-MS (concentration)	LC-MS (concentration)	
Tetrahydrocannabinol	0.16 to 2.3 ng/mg	0.01 to 10 ng/mg	(Khajuria & Nayak, 2014; Shah et al., 2019)
THC-COOH	0.05 to 0.80 ng/mg	0.18 to 1.75 ng/mg	(Vaiano et al., 2023; Villamor et al., 2004)
Cannabidiol	0.01 to 15.26 ng/mg	0.01 to 15.26 ng/mg	(Scholz et al., 2022; Villamor et al., 2004)
Cannabinol	0.03 to 6.66 ng/mg	0.022 to 2.562 ng/mg	(Al-Zahrani et al., 2021; Villamor et al., 2004)
Cocaine	0.2 to 5.0 ng/mg	0.05 ng/mg	(Janna Anichina et al., 2019; López-Guarnido et al., 2013)

Table I presents an analytical data comparison wherein drugs were extracted by various experts employing distinct modes of instrumentation, including both GC-MS and LC-MS. The comparative analysis of analytical detection using GC-MS and LC-MS reveals that LC-MS generally offers higher sensitivity, particularly for detecting lower concentrations of drugs and their metabolites. For instance, LC-MS can detect tetrahydrocannabinol (THC) as low as 0.01 ng/mg, compared to 0.16 ng/mg by GC-MS, and detects cocaine at 0.05 ng/mg, outperforming GC-MS's lower limit of 0.2 ng/mg. While both techniques demonstrate equal efficiency for cannabidiol (CBD) detection, GC-MS shows better sensitivity for THC-COOH at the lower range (0.05 ng/mg vs. 0.18 ng/mg in LC-MS). For cannabinol, LC-MS again surpasses GC-MS in lower detection capability (0.022 ng/mg vs. 0.03 ng/mg). Overall, LC-MS is more effective for trace-level detection, making it particularly suitable for forensic toxicology and drug screening, while GC-MS remains valuable for confirmatory analysis and detection of higher concentration ranges.

10.9.2. Liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry:

In drug hair analysis, liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) has emerged as a crucial analytical technique that complements gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), offering several advantages for identification and measurement of drugs and their metabolites in hair samples. The increased sensitivity and specificity of LC-MS enable the detection of drugs at very low concentrations, including trace amounts, which represents a significant advantage (Kintz et al., 2004; Kintz & Cirimele, 1997).

Researchers reported the first forensic case of detecting the designer drug 2C-B – a new psychoactive

substance (NPS), in hair using high-resolution liquid chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry, accentuating the technique's exceptional sensitivity (Mathey et al., 2021). This becomes particularly important during analysis of polar or thermally labile chemical compounds that are not suitable for GC-MS analysis. Additionally, the quantitative capabilities of LC-MS allow accurate determination of the drug concentrations in hair samples.

The use of tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS) further enhances selectivity and accuracy in drug detection, as MS/MS fragmentation patterns supports accurate identification of pharmaceuticals and their

metabolites (kintz et al.,2024; kintz & Cirimele,1997). Moreover, LC-MS allows the use of isotopically labeled internal standards, ensuring precise quantification and enhancing the reliability and reproducibility of results (Dumestre-Toulet et al.,2002). This technique can be applied in numerous ranges of contexts including legal investigations, workplace drug testing, and monitoring drug compliance in substance abuse treatment programs (Auwärter et al.,2001).

10.9.3. Other methods for drug hair analysis:

Although mass spectrometry is widely considered as the gold standard for forensic hair analysis in drug identification, GC and HPLC-based methods have also shown promise as alternative detection methods (Pichini et al.,2004). For instance, GC with nitrogen-phosphorus detection (NPD) has proven effective in detecting substances such as amphetamines and chloroquine. Similarly, gas chromatography with electron capture detection (GC-ECD) has been used to identify organochloride adulterants.

High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) with UV detection has also been used for medications such as indinavir, lamotrigine, phenytoin, and carbamazepine. Haloperidol has also been analysed using HPLC with ECD. Additionally, ciprofloxacin and its analogs, flecainide, and 5-fluorouracil following derivatization have all been detected using HPLC with luminescence detection. Most of the time, the drug concentration was more than 1 ng/mg. Notably, one instance where an alternate methodology worked better than MS-based methods is the measurement of LSD utilizing HPLC with luminescence detection following separation by immunoabsorption.

These diverse detection systems provide valuable options for drug detection and quantification in hair samples, delivering reliable results in various forensic and clinical applications (Thiblin et al., 2000).

10. INTERPRETATION OF ANALYTICAL OUTCOMES

When interpreting the outcomes of qualitative and quantitative analyses, several questions may arise, contributing to a more precise understanding of the results. Some of these questions include:

1. What specific drug was consumed?
2. When was the drug been consumed?
3. Is the person a regular or occasional drug user?

Answers to these questions cannot solely rely on analytical techniques; they also require the expertise of the examiner.

Drawing on previous studies and experiments conducted by examiners, it has been established that certain individuals did not actively take the drug but instead, the drugs were passively absorbed through hair due to being in the company of drug consumers or exposure to various drug-related environments.

Hair drug test results for 107 children under the age of 12 who were suspected of being exposed to methamphetamine production by their caretakers were examined in an illustrative study. To verify the findings, gas chromatography-mass spectrometry was used. 36% of the 107 children were younger than three years old, as evidenced by the 103 who had enough hair samples for analysis. Children with both light and dark hair had positive hair drug test results for the combination of amphetamine and methamphetamine. Therefore, determining whether the intake was active or passive relies on the concentrations in the hair wash extract. Inhibitors such as shampoo can also influence the results.

11. CONCLUSION

The findings of this study have suggested that, LC-MS as more sensitive and selective, specially for low-dose compounds and thermolabile substances, while GC-MS remains invaluable for confirmatory analytes. This study is very significant for clinical and forensic toxicological applications, providing important information about drug-use timeline, exposure types (active vs. passive), and minimizing false positives through proper pre-analytical decontamination and segmentation protocols. Future advancement should focus on standardization of decontamination protocols, improved detection through HR-MS (High resolution-mass spectrometry), and integration of machine learning for more accurate interpretation. More focus on regulatory harmonization and inter-laboratory validation will establish scientific credibility and legal admissibility of hair analysis in toxicological investigations.

12. REFERENCES

- 1. Aanstoos, C. M. (2024).** Recreational drugs. <https://Www.Ebsco.Com/>.
- 2. Al-Zahrani, M. A., Al-Asmari, A. I., Al-Zahrani, F. F., Torrance, H. J., & Watson, D. G. (2021).** Quantification of cannabinoids in human hair using a modified derivatization procedure and liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry. *Drug Testing and Analysis*, 13(6), 1095–1107. <https://doi.org/10.1002/dta.3005>.
- 3. Annamalai, J., Ganesan, S., Murugan, K., & Janjaroen, D. (2023).** Recent breakthroughs set by fungal enzymes in the biosynthesis of nanoparticles. In *Fungal Cell Factories for Sustainable Nanomaterials Productions and Agricultural Applications* (pp. 131–162). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-99922-9.00014-3>.
- 4. Asif Khan. (2023).** Pharmaceuticals Refer to a Category of Medical Products That are Designed to Diagnose. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Toxicology*, 6(4), 128–131. <https://www.openaccessjournals.com/articles/pharmaceuticals-refer-to-a-category-of-medical-products-that-are-designed-to-diagnose.pdf>
- 5. Aubry, A.-F. (2002).** Applications of affinity chromatography to the study of drug–melanin binding interactions. *Journal of Chromatography B*, 768(1), 67–74. DOI: [10.1016/S0378-4347\(01\)00486-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-4347(01)00486-8)
- 6. Auwärter, V., Sporkert, F., Hartwig, S., Pragst, F., Vater, H., & Diefenbacher, A. (2001).** Fatty acid ethyl esters in hair as markers of alcohol consumption. Segmental hair analysis of alcoholics, social drinkers, and teetotalers. *Clinical Chemistry*, 47(12), 2114–2123. PMID: [11719475](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/11719475/).
- 7. Bani, K. S., & Bhardwaj, K. (2021).** Topical Drug Delivery Therapeutics, Drug Absorption and Penetration Enhancement Techniques. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, 11(4), 105–110. <https://doi.org/10.22270/jddt.v11i4.4864>.
- 8. Barroso, M., & Gallardo, E. (2014).** Hair Analysis for Forensic Applications: is The Future Bright? *Bioanalysis*, 6(1), 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.4155/bio.13.291>
- 9. Begun, A. L., & Murray, M. M. (Eds.). (2020).** *The Routledge Handbook of Social Work and Addictive Behaviors*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429203121>
- 10. Benet, L. Z. (1978).** Effect of route of administration and distribution on drug action. *Journal of Pharmacokinetics and Biopharmaceutics*, 6(6), 559–585. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01062110>
- 11. Benjamin, A., & Chidi, N. (2014).** Drug abuse, addiction and dependence. *Pharmacology and Therapeutics*. In-Tech. doi: [10.5772/58574](https://doi.org/10.5772/58574)
- 12. Bertol, E., & Favretto, D. (2022).** Pharmacokinetics: Drug Absorption, Distribution, and Elimination. In *Karch's Drug Abuse Handbook* (pp. 133–178). CRC Press. 3rd Edition. eBook ISBN9781315155159
- 13. Bhowmik, D. (2012).** Recent advances in novel topical drug delivery system. *The Pharma Innovation*, 1(9). <https://www.thepharmajournal.com/archives/2012/vol1issue9/PartA/1.1.pdf>
- 14. Bird, D., & Ravindra, N. M. (2020).** Transdermal drug delivery and patches—An overview. *MEDICAL DEVICES & SENSORS*, 3(6). <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/mds3.10069>
- 15. Boumba, V. A., Ziavrou, K. S., & Vougiouklakis, T. (2006).** Hair as a Biological Indicator of Drug Use, Drug Abuse or Chronic Exposure to Environmental Toxicants. *International Journal of Toxicology*, 25(3), 143–163. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10915810600683028>
- 16. Burke-Shyne, N., Csete, J., Wilson, D., Fox, E., Wolfe, D., & Rasanathan, J. J. K. (2017).** How drug control policy and practice undermine access to controlled medicines. *Health and Human Rights*, 19(1), 237. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5473053/pdf/hhr-19-237.pdf>
- 17. Cairns, T., Hill, V., Schaffer, M., & Thistle, W. (2004).** Levels of cocaine and its metabolites in washed hair of demonstrated cocaine users and workplace subjects. *Forensic Science International*, 145(2–3), 175–181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forsciint.2004.04.033>
- 18. Chourasia, R., & Jain, S. K. (2009).** Drug targeting through pilosebaceous route. *Current Drug Targets*, 10(10), 950–967. DOI: [10.2174/138945009789577918](https://doi.org/10.2174/138945009789577918).
- 19. Cirimele, V., Kintz, P., Staub, C., & Mangin, P. (1997).** Testing human hair for flunitrazepam and 7-amino-flunitrazepam by GC/MS-NCI. *Forensic Science International*, 84(1–3), 189–200. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0379-0738\(96\)02062-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0379-0738(96)02062-2).
- 20. Cone, E. J. (1996).** Mechanisms of Drug Incorporation into Hair. *Therapeutic Drug Monitoring*, 18(4), 438–443. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00007691-199608000-00022>

- 21. Cone, E. J., Yousefnejad, D., Darwin, W. D., & Maguire, T. (1991).** Testing Human Hair for Drugs of Abuse. II. Identification of Unique Cocaine Metabolites in Hair of Drug Abusers and Evaluation of Decontamination Procedures. *Journal of Analytical Toxicology*, 15(5), 250–255. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jat/15.5.250>.
- 22. del Ramírez Fernández, M. del M., Barroso, M., & Andraus, M. (2025).** Global Trends and Methodological Challenges in Hair Toxicology: A Survey-Based Analysis. *Drug Testing and Analysis*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/dta.3879>
- 23. Drug delivery systems. (2015).** In *Strategies to Modify the Drug Release from Pharmaceutical Systems* (pp. 87–194). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-100092-2.00006-0>
- 24. Dumestre-Toulet, V., Cirimele, V., Ludes, B., Gromb, S., & Kintz, P. (2002).** Hair analysis of seven bodybuilders for anabolic steroids, ephedrine, and clenbuterol. *Journal of Forensic Sciences*, 47(1), 211–214.
- 25. DuPont, R. L., & Baumgartner, W. A. (1995).** Drug testing by urine and hair analysis: complementary features and scientific issues. *Forensic Science International*, 70(1–3), 63–76. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0379-0738\(94\)01625-F](https://doi.org/10.1016/0379-0738(94)01625-F)
- 26. Farah, H. A. (2020).** The effect of heat and chemical penetration enhancers on the follicular absorption of topically applied drugs. 37(6):112. [doi: 10.1007/s11095-020-02822-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11095-020-02822-y).
- 27. Fernández, M. del M. R., Baumgartner, W. A., Wille, S. M. R., Farabee, D., Samyn, N., & Baumgartner, A. M. (2020).** A different insight in hair analysis: Simultaneous measurement of antipsychotic drugs and metabolites in the protein and melanin fraction of hair from criminal justice patients. *Forensic Science International*. 312:110337. [doi: 10.1016/j.forsciint.2020.110337](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forsciint.2020.110337). Epub 2020 May 19.
- 28. Flynn, G. L. (1996).** Cutaneous and transdermal delivery—processes and systems of delivery. In *Modern Pharmaceutics Revised and Expanded* (pp. 314–385). CRC Press.
- 29. General considerations. (2015).** In *Strategies to Modify the Drug Release from Pharmaceutical Systems* (pp. 1–14). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-100092-2.00001-1>
- 30. Goullé, J. P., Chèze, M., & Pépin, G. (2003).** Determination of Endogenous Levels of GHB in Human Hair. Are there Possibilities for the Identification of GHB Administration through Hair Analysis in Cases of Drug-Facilitated Sexual Assault? *Journal of Analytical Toxicology*, 27(8), 574–580. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jat/27.8.574>
- 31. Harkey, M. R. (1993).** Anatomy and physiology of hair. *Forensic Science International*, 63(1–3), 9–18. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0379-0738\(93\)90255-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0379-0738(93)90255-9)
- 32. Hedaya, M. A. (2024).** Routes of Drug Administration. In *Pharmaceutics* (pp. 537–554). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-99796-6.00006-0>
- 33. Hung, S.-H., Kan, H.-L., Tung, C.-W., Lin, Y.-C., Chen, T.-T., Tian, C., & Chang, W. C.-W. (2024).** Probing the hair detectability of prohibited substances in sports: an in vivo-in silico-clinical approach and analytical implications compared with plasma, urine, and faeces. *Archives of Toxicology*, 98(3), 779–790. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00204-023-03667-1>.
- 34. Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Health Care (IQWiG). (2006).** Using medication: Learn More – Oral medications. InformedHealth.Org [Internet]. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK279445/>
- 35. Janna Anichina, Oscar G. Cabrices, Sean Orłowicz, Laura Snow, & Pierre Negri. (2019).** Ultra-Sensitive Forensic Analysis of Cocaine and its Metabolites in Hair Samples. <https://sciex.com/tech-notes/forensic/toxicology/ultra-sensitive-forensic-analysis-workflow-of-cocaine-and-its-me>
- 36. Jasti, B. R., Abraham, W., & Ghosh, T. K. (2021).** Transdermal and Topical drug delivery systems. In *Theory and practice of contemporary pharmaceutics* (pp. 423–454). CRC Press. [eBook ISBN9780203644478](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-203-64447-8)
- 37. Palmer, J. (2024).** Advancing the Development of Macrocyclic Peptide Therapeutics Using High-Throughput Mass Spectrometry Approaches (Doctoral dissertation, University of Washington).
- 38. Joseph, R. E., Su, T.-P., & Cone, E. J. (1996).** In Vitro Binding Studies of Drugs to Hair: Influence of Melanin and Lipids on Cocaine Binding to Caucoid and Africoid Hair. *Journal of Analytical Toxicology*, 20(6), 338–344. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jat/20.6.338>.
- 39. Khajuria, H., & Nayak, B. P. (2014).** Detection of Δ9-tetrahydrocannabinol (THC) in hair using GC–MS. *Egyptian Journal of Forensic Sciences*, 4(1), 17–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejfs.2013.10.001>
- 40. Kintz, P. (2003).** Testing for anabolic steroids in

hair: a review. *Legal Medicine*, 5, S29–S33. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1344-6223\(02\)00085-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1344-6223(02)00085-8)

41. Kintz, P., & Cirimele, V. (1997). Interlaboratory comparison of quantitative determination of amphetamine and related compounds in hair samples. *Forensic Science International*, 84(1–3), 151–156. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0379-0738\(96\)02058-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0379-0738(96)02058-0).

42. Kintz, P., Villain, M., & Cirimele, V. (2006). Hair Analysis for Drug Detection. *Therapeutic Drug Monitoring*, 28(3), 442–446. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.ftd.0000211811.27558.b5>.

43. Kintz, P., Villain, M., Cirimele, V., Pépin, G., & Ludes, B. (2004). Windows of detection of lorazepam in urine, oral fluid and hair, with a special focus on drug-facilitated crimes. *Forensic Science International*, 145(2–3), 131–135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forsciint.2004.04.027>.

44. Klein, J., Karaskov, T., & Koren, G. (2000). Clinical applications of hair testing for drugs of abuse — the Canadian experience. *Forensic Science International*, 107(1–3), 281–288. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0379-0738\(99\)00171-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0379-0738(99)00171-1)

45. Larsson, B., & Tjälve, H. (1979). Studies on the mechanism of drug-binding to melanin. *Biochemical Pharmacology*, 28(7), 1181–1187. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-2952\(79\)90326-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-2952(79)90326-5).

46. López-Guarnido, O., Álvarez, I., Gil, F., Rodrigo, L., Cataño, H. C., Bermejo, A. M., Tabernero, M. J., Pla, A., & Hernández, A. F. (2013). Hair testing for cocaine and metabolites by GC/MS: criteria to quantitatively assess cocaine use. *Journal of Applied Toxicology*, 33(8), 838–844. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jat.2741>

47. Matey, J. M., López-Fernández, A., García-Ruiz, C., Montalvo, G., Zapata, F., & Martínez, M. A. (2021). Identification of 2C-B in Hair by UHPLC-HRMS/MS. A Real Forensic Case. *Toxics*, 9(7), 170. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxics9070170>

48. Mayo Clinic Staff. (2025). Drug Addiction (substance use disorder). <https://www.mayoclinic.org/>.

49. Mieczkowski, T., & Kruger, M. (2007). Interpreting the color effect of melanin on cocaine and benzoylecgonine assays for hair analysis: Brown and black samples compared. *Journal of Forensic and Legal Medicine*, 14(1), 7–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcfm.2005.09.004>

50. Mizuno, A., Uematsu, T., & Nakashima, M. (1994). Simultaneous determination of ofloxacin, norfloxacin and ciprofloxacin in human hair by high-performance liquid chromatography and fluorescence detection. *Journal of Chromatography B: Biomedical Sciences and Applications*, 653(2), 187–193. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-4347\(93\)E0440-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-4347(93)E0440-2)

51. NT CONTRIBUTOR. (2003). SKILLS – INTRAMUSCULAR INJECTIONS. https://www.rch.org.au/rchcpg/hospital_clinical_guideline_index/Intramuscular_Injections/

52. Oluwole, I. S., ISHOLA, A. G., OJO, I. O., & BABARI-MISA, O. (2024). Risk Factors and Consequences of Drug Abuse Among Undergraduate Students. Volume: 5, Issue: 6, Year: 2024 Page: 47-63 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14609260.

53. Palamar, J. J., & Salomone, A. (2023). On the challenges of hair testing to detect underreported substance use in research settings. *The American Journal of Drug and Alcohol Abuse*, 49(1), 1–4. [doi: 10.1080/00952990.2023.2166414](https://doi.org/10.1080/00952990.2023.2166414).

54. Papaseit, E., Joya, X., Velasco, M., Civit, E., Mota, P., Bertran, M., Vall, O., & Garcia-Algar, O. (2011). Hair analysis following chronic smoked-drugs-of-abuse exposure in adults and their toddler: a case report. *Journal of Medical Case Reports*, 5(1), 570. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1752-1947-5-570>

55. Patton, J. S., & Byron, P. R. (2007). Inhaling medicines: delivering drugs to the body through the lungs. *Nature Reviews Drug Discovery*, 6(1), 67–74. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrd2153>

56. Patzelt, A., & Lademann, J. (2013). Drug delivery to hair follicles. *Expert Opinion on Drug Delivery*, 10(6), 787–797. <https://doi.org/10.1517/17425247.2013.776038>.

57. Pichini, S., Ventura, M., Pujadas, M., Ventura, R., Pellegrini, M., Zuccaro, P., Pacifici, R., & de la Torre, R. (2004). HAIRVEQ: an external quality control scheme for drugs of abuse analysis in hair. *Forensic Science International*, 145(2–3), 109–115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forsciint.2004.04.025>

58. Pragst, F., & Balikova, M. A. (2006). State of the art in hair analysis for detection of drug and alcohol abuse. *Clinica Chimica Acta*, 370(1–2), 17–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cca.2006.02.019>

59. Preuss, C. V, Kalava, A., & King, K. C. (2019). Pre-
<https://iftspublisher.co.in/ojs/index.php/>

scription of controlled substances: benefits and risks. <https://www.statpearls.com/point-of-care/40661>

60. Röhrich, J., & Kauert, G. (1997). Determination of amphetamine and methylenedioxy-amphetamine-derivatives in hair. *Forensic Science International*, 84(1–3), 179–188. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0379-0738\(96\)02061-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0379-0738(96)02061-0)

61. Rotolo, M. C., Pacifici, R., Pellegrini, M., Cardullo, S., Pérez, L. J. G., Cuppone, D., Gallimberti, L., & Madeo, G. (2021). Hair Testing for Classic Drugs of Abuse to Monitor Cocaine Use Disorder in Patients Following Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation Protocol Treatment. *Biology*, 10(5), 403. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biology10050403>

62. Scholz, C., Madry, M. M., Kraemer, T., & Baumgartner, M. R. (2022). LC–MS-MS Analysis of Δ^9 -THC, CBN and CBD in Hair: Investigation of Artifacts. *Journal of Analytical Toxicology*, 46(5), 504–511. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jat/bkab056>

63. Seear, K. (2024). Shifting solutions: Tracking transformations of drugs, health and the ‘human’ through human rights processes in Australia. *Health Sociology Review*, 33(3), 257–272. doi: 10.1080/14461242.2023.2254746. Epub 2023 Sep 20.

64. Shah, I., Al-Dabbagh, B., Salem, A. E., Hamid, S. A. A., Muhammad, N., & Naughton, D. P. (2019). A review of bioanalytical techniques for evaluation of cannabis (Marijuana, weed, Hashish) in human hair. *BMC Chemistry*, 13(1), 106. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13065-019-0627-2>

65. Skopp, G., Pötsch, L., & Moeller, M. R. (1997). On cosmetically treated hair — aspects and pitfalls of interpretation. *Forensic Science International*, 84(1–3), 43–52. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0379-0738\(96\)02047-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0379-0738(96)02047-6)

66. Spiehler, V. (2000). Hair analysis by immunological methods from the beginning to 2000. *Forensic Science International*, 107(1–3), 249–259. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0379-0738\(99\)00168-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0379-0738(99)00168-1)

67. Srogi, K. (2006). Hair Analysis as Method for Determination of Level of Drugs and Pharmaceutical in Human Body: Review of Chromatographic Procedures. *Analytical Letters*, 39(2), 231–258. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00032710500476821>

68. Tagliaro, F., Valentini, R., Manetto, G., Crivellente, F., Carli, G., & Marigo, M. (2000). Hair analysis by using radioimmunoassay, high-performance liquid chromatography and capillary electrophoresis to investigate chronic exposure

to heroin, cocaine and/or ecstasy in applicants for driving licences. *Forensic Science International*, 107(1–3), 121–128. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0379-0738\(99\)00157-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0379-0738(99)00157-7)

69. Thiblin, I., Lindquist, O., & Rajs, J. (2000). Cause and manner of death among users of anabolic androgenic steroids. *Journal of Forensic Sciences*, 45(1), 16–23. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/10641914/>

70. Thorspecken, J., Skopp, G., & Pötsch, L. (2004). In Vitro Contamination of Hair by Marijuana Smoke. *Clinical Chemistry*, 50(3), 596–602. <https://doi.org/10.1373/clinchem.2003.026120>

71. Tiwari, C., Choudhary, M., Malik, P., JAISWAL, P. K., & Chauhan, R. (2022). Transdermal Patch: A Novel Approach for Transdermal Drug Delivery. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, 12(6), 179–188. <https://doi.org/10.22270/jddt.v12i6.5779>

72. Usman, M., Naseer, A., Baig, Y., Jamshaid, T., Shahwar, M., & Khurshuid, S. (2019). Forensic toxicological analysis of hair: a review. *Egyptian Journal of Forensic Sciences*, 9(1), 17. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41935-019-0119-5>

73. Vaiano, F., Scuffi, L., Lachi, A., Trignano, C., Argo, A., Mari, F., & Bertol, E. (2023). THC and THC-COOH hair concentrations: Influence of age, gender, consumption habits, cosmetics treatment, and hair features. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*, 225, 115237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpba.2023.115237>

74. Villamor, J. L., Bermejo, A. M., Tabernero, M. J., & Fernández, P. (2004). Determination of Cannabinoids in Human Hair by GC/MS. *Analytical Letters*, 37(3), 517–528. <https://doi.org/10.1081/AL-120028624>

75. Wang, W. L., & Cone, E. J. (1995). Testing human hair for drugs of abuse. IV. Environmental cocaine contamination and washing effects. *Forensic Science International*, 70(1–3), 39–51. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0379-0738\(94\)01616-D](https://doi.org/10.1016/0379-0738(94)01616-D)

76. Welch, M. J., Sniegowski, L. T., Allgood, C. C., & Habram, M. (1993). Hair Analysis for Drugs of Abuse: Evaluation of Analytical Methods, Environmental Issues, and Development of Reference Materials*. *Journal of Analytical Toxicology*, 17(7), 389–398. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jat/17.7.389>

77. Wissenbach, D. K., & Steuer, A. E. (2023). Advances in testing for sample manipulation in clinical and forensic toxicology.

cology - Part A: urine samples. *Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry*, 415(21), 5101–5115. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-023-04711-w>

78. Yan, H., Xiang, P., & Shen, M. (2021). Current status of hair analysis in forensic toxicology in China. *Forensic Sciences Research*, 6(3), 240–249. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20961790.2021.1921945>

79. Yu, Y.-Q., Yang, X., Wu, X.-F., & Fan, Y.-B. (2021). Enhancing Permeation of Drug Molecules Across the Skin via Delivery in Nanocarriers: Novel Strategies for Effective Transdermal Applications. *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2021.646554>